

Issue Tracker 2024/004
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[Ascidian Therapeutics, Roche Enter Research Collaboration & License Agreement:](#) Ascidian Therapeutics, a biotechnology company focused on rewriting DNA to treat human diseases, has entered into a collaboration and licensing agreement with Roche to use Ascidian's RNA exon editing platform to treat neurological diseases. Ascidian remains responsible for discovery and preclinical activities while Roche will handle clinical development, manufacturing and commercialization of developed treatments.

[Call for incoming Parliament not to raise barriers to open scientific cooperation:](#) A joint statement by presidents of national academies of science in all EU member states urges the incoming European Parliament to avoid raising barriers to open scientific cooperation. They stress the importance of maintaining the EU's global leadership in science by promoting open science, boosting R&D investment, and ensuring academic freedom and institutional autonomy. The academies emphasize the need to avoid isolating scientific collaboration due to geopolitical tensions and to increase investment to 3% of GDP for sustainable development.

[MilliporeSigma Contributes to Advancing Parkinson's Research:](#) MilliporeSigma, through funding from the Michael J. Fox Foundation, has developed a SMCxPRO immunoassay that can detect low levels of a biomarker associated with cell dysfunction in Parkinson's patients. The technology is being made available to the scientific community for use in Parkinson's research, which up until this time had been unable to track the response of different treatments on disease progression.

[Two new pilot schemes to improve clinical trials applications in EU:](#) The Accelerating Clinical Trials in the EU initiative has launched two pilot programs to improve clinical trial design. The first offers advice to biotech companies on clinical trials and how to successfully file marketing authorization applications, while the other provides technical and regulatory support clinical trial applications through the European Medicines Agency's Clinical Trials Information System, which includes a publicly searchable database.

[Researchers uncover enzyme communication mechanism that could aid drug development:](#) The Integrative Structural Biology team at the University of Birmingham has pinpointed a communication mechanism between proteins in enzymes that produce organic molecules. This opens the door to exploring methods to stimulate the creation of natural products that have disease-fighting capabilities and could provide a potential solution to combatting rising antimicrobial resistance.